

Data Handling for the Navy's Hyperspectral Imaging Satellite—NEMO¹

William S. Vincent
Naval Research Laboratory
4555 Overlook Ave SW
Washington, DC 20375-5355
202-404-7315
vincent@space.nrl.navy.mil

Abstract—The Office of Naval Research, the Naval Research Laboratory, and commercial partner Space Technology Development Corporation are currently in the critical design phase of the Naval EarthMap Observer (NEMO) spacecraft program. NEMO will demonstrate the utility of a hyperspectral earth-imaging system to support Naval needs for characterization of the littoral (coastal ocean) regions of the world and commercial needs for land use management, agriculture, environmental studies, and mineral exploration. Data handling from user request to data delivery is one of the many challenges posed by NEMO. The NEMO program must be able to accept data requests from users, create spacecraft tasking, collect data from the spacecraft, process and archive the data, provide access for users to browse collected imagery, and deliver processed data products to these users. Some of these steps will employ unique approaches due to the nature of hyperspectral imagery data.

features such as fronts, bars, and reefs that are typically on the scale of a few hundred meters. The 10 nm spectral resolution is required to detect many of the ocean and land spectral absorption features, which are on the order of 20 to 40 nm in width.

In a collaborative effort with the University of South Florida, NRL has demonstrated the use of AVIRIS data to separate the chlorophyll signal from bottom reflectance in the clear waters of Lake Tahoe [4] and the turbid waters offshore from Tampa Bay [5]. In addition, spectral signals from resuspended sediments and dissolved organics have been interpreted for the Tampa Bay AVIRIS images [5,6] and for suspended sediments and kelp beds for AVIRIS images of San Pedro Channel [7]. These results lead to a general semi-analytical model for decomposition of the spectral signatures [8,9].

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1. BACKGROUND

The Navy is in the midst of a fundamental shift away from open ocean, deep water operations to joint littoral warfare. To support that effort, the Navy and Marine Corps need precise information in denied areas regarding shallow water bathymetry, bottom type composition, detection of underwater hazards, water clarity, and visibility [1]. Visible radiation is part of the electromagnetic spectrum that penetrates water, and passive optical systems can provide these products from space.

To address the problems of the coastal ocean, NRL has been working since 1990 using the Airborne Visible/Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) [2,3] which is operated by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory and flown on an ER-2 operated by NASA Ames. AVIRIS data provide 20 m spatial resolution and 200 spectral bands covering a 0.4 to 2.4 μm spectral range at 10 nm resolution. The 20 m spatial resolution provides the ability to observe coastal

Similar progress has been made on the land applications of imaging spectrometer data since the value of that data was first highlighted in an article in *Science* in 1985 [10]. Primarily using AVIRIS data, applications have been developed for the retrieval of atmospheric properties [11] and for assessing crop status, environmental quality, and mineral exploration. In particular, mineral exploration has become a hot topic. Some of the leading scientists in this area have formed Analytical and Imaging Geophysics Limited Liability Co. (AIGC, Boulder, Colorado) to use AVIRIS and/or other imaging spectrometer data for mineral exploration, and they have a growing list of mining and oil company clients.

Spacebased multispectral imagers, such as Landsat (6 bands, 450–2350 nm and 1 band, 10.4–12.5 μm) and SeaWiFS, (8 bands, 400–800 nm) lack sufficient spectral resolution to distinguish between the many different complex spectral signatures present in a coastal ocean or during mineral exploration. Hyperspectral imaging spectrometers do resolve those signatures and are an ideal tool to fill these requirements, but have not been used from space to date because of cost and the demands of data downlink and processing. Approaches to overcome both these problems have recently become available.

Figure 1 shows a general description of the imaging spectrometry concept.

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Figure 1 Imaging Spectrometry Concept

Joint DoD Commercial Program

To demonstrate the utility of hyperspectral imaging from space the Naval EarthMap Observer (NEMO) program was established. NEMO is a joint government and industry effort between the Space Technology Development Corporation (STDC) and its government partner, the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL), and is sponsored by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) and the Defense Advanced Research Project Agency's (DARPA's) Joint Dual Use Applications Program.

NRL and STDC play complementary roles in the NEMO program. NRL provides the design of the NEMO sensors and their integration with the commercial satellite bus, bus modifications, the on-board processor, the Optical Real-time Adaptive Spectral Identification System (ORASIS), and systems engineering. In addition, data products and algorithms, e.g., bathymetry, K490, bottom type, water clarity, and models for the Naval warfighter, are being developed by the Navy. STDC and its Industry Partners provide the commercial satellite bus, selected components, launch services, and flight operations. STDC's EarthMap will provide a broad market presence and support its customer base with cost-effective access to a broad variety of Hyperspectral Imagery (HSI) data with applications for government and commercial users. EarthMap will provide a range of geographic information system products and services, including data collection, processing, conversion, archiving, and distribution.

Program Objectives

The primary function of the NEMO program is to develop and fly a satellite-borne earth observing HSI system to provide HSI data and to process the data to meet Naval and commercial requirements. The mission objectives are as follows:

- Demonstrate use of hyperspectral imagery for the characterization of the littoral battlespace environment and littoral model development.
- Demonstrate automated, on-board processing, analysis, and feature extraction using ORASIS.
- Demonstrate the value of hyperspectral data for DoD operations and commercial applications.
- Demonstrate support to the warfighter with real-time tactical downlink of hyperspectral end products directly from the spacecraft to the field.

Naval Requirements

NEMO meets the unique requirements of Naval Forces by imaging the littoral regions of the world in 210 spectral bands over a 0.4 to 2.5 µm bandpass with a very high Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR). NEMO has the goal of characterizing the dynamics of the littoral environment through the use of hyperspectral imagery and the development of coupled physical and bio-optical models of the littoral ocean. The collected images provide the observational data essential in any efforts to model the littoral environment. Of specific importance to the Navy is development of validated algorithms that use NEMO data to determine water clarity, bathymetry, underwater hazards, currents, oil slicks, bottom type, atmospheric visibility, tides, bioluminescence potential, beach characterization, atmospheric water vapor, and subvisible cirrus along with terrestrial images of vegetation and soil. These data support identified requirements for Joint Strike and Joint Littoral warfare, particularly for environmental characterization of the littoral ocean and intelligent preparation of the battlespace for amphibious assault.

NEMO Mission Description

The NEMO spacecraft will be launched into Low Earth Orbit (LEO) in mid-2000. The spacecraft will be placed in a sun-synchronous (97.81 degree inclination) orbit at 605 km altitude with a 10:30 a.m. ascending equator crossing. This orbit will provide a 7-day repeat coverage ability to allow, at a minimum, weekly access to any point on the earth. The 10:30 a.m. orbital crossing ensures consistent image quality and minimal cloud cover.

Table 1 provides a general overview of the NEMO program mission characteristics.

Spacecraft Payload

The sensor complement flown on the NEMO spacecraft includes a Coastal Ocean Imaging Spectrometer (COIS) and a co-registered Panchromatic Imaging Camera (PIC). The primary challenges in the COIS design are the wide field of view (>2.5 degrees) and the very high SNR [200:1 Very Near Infrared (VNIR), 100:1 Short Wave Infrared (SWIR)], particularly near the blue end (0.4 µm) of the spectrum

required for ocean imaging. NEMO also employs NRL's ORASIS, an automated end-to-end HSI data processing system that will significantly reduce the amount of data NEMO must transmit to the ground.

Table 1 Mission Characteristics

Item	Parameter
Launch	Third Quarter, FY00
Orbit	605 km sun synchronous (97.81 degrees) 10:30 am equatorial crossing (ascending)
Repeat Global Coverage	7 day repeat, 2.5 day global average reaccess
Spectral Range	0.4 to 2.5 μm at 10 nm spectral resolution (210 bands)
Signal-to-Noise	>200 over 0.4 to 1.0 μm for a 5% reflectance target
Lifetime	3 year mission life (80% probability based on PDR level reliability analysis) 5 year design life (50% probability based on PDR level reliability analysis)
Data Rates	150 Mbps X-Band imagery and telemetry downlink (normal mode) 16 Mbps X-Band telemetry downlink (emergency mode) 1 Mbps S-Band imagery downlink for tactical demonstration 2 kbps S-Band command uplink
Data	Estimated average daily imagery data \approx 227 Gbits (capability of \approx 500 Gbits) 48 Gbit on-board storage
On-Board Processing	Real-Time feature extraction and classification with >10x data reduction using ORASIS

Table 2 provides the characteristics of the NEMO sensor system.

Optical Real-time Adaptive Spectral Identification System (ORASIS)

NEMO employs NRL's automated end-to-end HSI data processing system called ORASIS. ORASIS is unique and, like the hyperspectral sensor itself, critical to the viability of the program. ORASIS offers automated and adaptive signature recognition capability, improving the operational efficiency to analyze both military and commercial data sets. It is important to note that while ORASIS is fully automated, it is also computationally intensive, requiring the NEMO satellite to have an on-board processor with GigaFLOP capability.

ORASIS is a high-speed processing system that identifies the spectral signatures corresponding to physical objects in the scene without supervision or *a priori* knowledge. The approach is to analyze each spectra in the scene sequentially, discarding duplicate spectra, and working only with the unique spectra and the map of their location in the scene. Using convex set methods and orthogonal projection techniques, each observed spectrum is then analyzed in terms of the set of vectors that represent the physically meaningful basis patterns that have combined to make the observed spectrum. Then matched filters (Filter Vectors) are created and used to demix the image [12,13].

ORASIS processing on board NEMO minimizes subsequent ground processing for data exploitation and maps of identified features, and enables the on-board production of data products. An important benefit of ORASIS processing is a greater than tenfold data compression (lossy), relieving hyperspectral data bottlenecks of on-board data storage and transmission to the ground. The losses introduced by ORASIS will be on the order of 1-2%. An early version of ORASIS was successfully flight demonstrated in a tactical environment in the recent COVERED LANTERN exercise, using hyperspectral images from a Pioneer Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle (UAV). This test proved ORASIS compression and detection capabilities.

ORASIS is implemented on the Imagery On-Board Processor (IOBP), an advanced high speed computer consisting of a highly parallel array of digital signal processors, capable of sustaining 2.5 GigaFLOPS. The ORASIS algorithm and the radiation tolerant IOBP allow the first demonstration of real-time processing of hyperspectral data in space. ORASIS will also be used as the basic spectral decomposition tool for the ground analysis of the HSI data and the production of Naval products.

2. NEMO DATA HANDLING

One of the many challenges in the NEMO program is data handling. Data handling includes all steps to deliver data to a user, starting with the user's request for data. Some of the steps required are typical of modern commercial imaging systems; however, hyperspectral data and the available onboard processing provide many unique opportunities for new approaches, particularly on the output side.

Figure 2 shows the Concept of Operations for NEMO Data Handling.

Data Requests

Data requests will be collected from various users including mission scientists, Naval operational users, government users, and commercial users. The primary means for making requests will be via a web-based interface. NRL will accept requests from government users and EarthMap will accept requests from commercial users. A user may specify a request in many ways. Users will be able to specify a point of interest by entering a specific latitude/longitude or by clicking on an interactive map via the web interface. Area requests for data will be made in a similar manner.

Table 2 Sensor Systems Characteristics

	VNIR	SWIR	PIC
Ground Sample Distance (GSD) (GMC: Ground Motion Compensation)	30 m with 5:1 GMC 60 m with no GMC	30 m with 5:1 GMC 60 m with no GMC	5 m (with or without GMC)
Spectral Range	0.4 to 1.0 μm	1.0 to 2.5 μm	0.5 to 0.7 μm
Signal-to-Noise Ratio (for 5% reflectance target)	>200 to 1	>100 to 1	>200 to 1
Swath Width	30 km	30 km	30 km
Swath Length	200 km @ 30 m GSD continuous @ 60 m GSD	200 km @ 30 m GSD continuous @ 60 m GSD	Continuous
Field of View	2.86 degrees	2.86 degrees	2.86 degrees

Figure 2 Concept of Operations

User requests will not necessarily translate directly into scene definitions that can be collected by NEMO. Spacecraft restrictions based on sensor swath widths, orbit geometries, and maneuver rates limit the ability for NEMO to image any random area definition. Both the Navy and commercial operation centers will be required to translate the user requests into scene definitions that NEMO can image. This process will be automated to the greatest extent possible. A grid system similar to Landsat's path/row system will be

applied for NEMO. This system will predefine a grid of scenes based on NEMO's 7 day repeating ground track. A user request will be converted into a series of these predefined scenes to satisfy the request.

In special cases, reserved primarily for the mission scientists and premium paying commercial customers, a more general scene definition may be used. By relaxing the constraint of the grid system, scene definitions that minimize the amount

of time required to image an area can be generated. In some cases, these custom scenes can collect the complete image of an area at one time. For Navy scientists a specific need for this capability exists when a rapidly changing phenomena (such as currents) needs to be observed in a single observation.

Scheduling

Once the Navy produces a set of scene definitions they will be prioritized based on the requestor and the timeliness of the event to be observed. This prioritized list of scene definitions is then forwarded to the EarthMap Operations Center (EOC). EarthMap will produce their own set of prioritized scene definitions based on the commercial user requests. Navy requests are then combined and deconflicted against commercial requests.

The deconfliction between the Navy and commercial requests is based on a process defined in the contract between the Navy and STDC. This contract defines a target as a scene that is 30 km wide by 200 km long and provides the ability for the Navy to task up to 25% of the targets that can be collected each day. The Navy's 25% tasking also has the highest priority when tasking requests are combined. There are detailed provisions in the contract that prevent the Navy from creating areas that cannot be imaged by EarthMap.

The combined and prioritized scene definition list is then sent to the mission planning function at the DataLynx Operations Center (DOC). DataLynx is a commercial satellite command, control, and communications service network from AlliedSignal. AlliedSignal is one of STDC's industry partners and is under contract to provide NEMO's mission operations and ground system segments.

Mission planning will schedule these scene definitions to be imaged based on predicted NEMO orbit tracks, request priorities, and engineering requirements on the spacecraft. The output of this mission planning system will be a time ordered list of images that NEMO can actually collect. The list of images will be entered into a rolling 14-day schedule that will allow daily command loads to be generated and long term planning to take place at the same time.

Spacecraft Operations

NEMO will be commanded once per day with a two-day command load. The daily command will include all engineering maintenance commands such as predicted state vectors, ground pass plans, maneuver loads, and sensor calibration procedures and the list of scenes to be imaged from the mission planning schedule. The two-day command load provides NEMO the ability to operate autonomously for two days. This capability provides a margin of safety if mission operations experiences an anomaly that prevents a ground command from occurring as scheduled.

As NEMO collects imagery, the normal mode of operations will flow the COIS hyperspectral data through the IOBP, which will produce ORASIS processed data files. These data files will then be stored on the Solid State Data

Recorder (SSDR). Simultaneously, the PIC data will be flowed into its own partition on the SSDR.

Although NEMO is only commanded once per day it will transmit data back to the ground up to 14 times per day. This is because the daily imaging command load will fill the SSDR many times over. Each time the SSDR is filled a ground pass is required to transmit this data to the ground site. NEMO will have one ground site provided by DataLynx in Fairbanks, Alaska at the time of launch. This single site will provide 9-10 downlink opportunities per day. Nine months after launch a second site will be made available. These two sites will provide up to 14 downlink opportunities per day.

Data downlinked to the ground site from NEMO will typically consist of a large volume (up to 48 Gbits) of imagery data and spacecraft telemetry data. Once received, telemetry data will be stripped off of the 150 Mbps stream and sent in real-time over a landline to the DOC. This data will immediately be processed to determine NEMO's state of health. Imagery data will be stored on a Redundant Array of Independent Disks (RAID) and then moved to a tape storage system. The tape storage system will most likely be a Digital Linear Tape (DLT) solution based on anticipated capacities of 100 GB per cartridge and 5-10 Mbyte/sec read/write rates available by 2000. Two tape copies of the data will be produced. The first tape will be picked up daily from the ground site and shipped via commercial carrier to the EarthMap Image Processing Center (IPC) in the Washington, DC area. The second tape will be maintained at the ground site for 7 days in order to allow verification of data receipt and integrity on the shipped tape.

Image Processing

The IPC is responsible for producing level 1B formatted data, archiving the data for STDC, and delivering a copy of all archived data to the Navy. Imagery data from the ground site will be delivered in a level 0 format. Level 0 data is identical to the data stored on the SSDR on the spacecraft. The IPC will process this data into level 1B data.

Table 3 defines all of the data levels used by the NEMO program.

As part of the level 1B Planetary Data System (PDS) archive directory structure, the IPC will be producing browse metadata products including a scene index database. The scene index database will identify the specific scenes that were imaged and provide information about each scene. The metadata correlated with each image data set will include pointing geometries that will identify where the scene was collected, the timing of the scene collection, and sensor and payload settings associated with the collection. In addition, a low resolution Red, Green, Blue (RGB) browse image and at least one (possibly two) low resolution cloud map will be generated for each image data set. Users will have some ability to look at a scene before requesting archived data.

Table 3 Data Level Definitions

Level	Definitions
Level 0	Imagery data identical to the stored on the spacecraft's SSDR. Panchromatic imagery may be raw or Rician compressed. Hyperspectral data may be raw hypercubes or ORASIS compressed data.
Level 1A	Level 0 data converted to standard image format with image header. The header includes pointing geometry information. Sample format are: Planetary Data system (PDS), National Imagery Transmission Format Standard (NITFS), or Flexible Image Transport System (FITS).
Level 1B	Level 1A data with estimates of calibration matrices to remove camera effects: gain, integration time, non-uniformities, constants to convert to apparent radiance.
Level 2	Level 1A data with calibration matrices applied and stored in a standard image format.
Level 3A	Level 2 data with atmospheric correction applied.
Level 3B	Map projected level 3A data.
Level 4	There are multiple products that are classified as level 4. These include bathymetry maps, water clarity maps, color dissolved organic matter maps, trafficability maps, or combined sensor data such as merged HSI and panchromatic data.

The current plans for the cloud map processing use unique hyperspectral features for the identification of scenes obscured by cloud cover. There are two methods under consideration for SWIR and VNIR data. Both methods can be completely automated and are intended as data filtering estimates rather than precise final data products.

The SWIR cloud percentage estimate will be based on the 1380 nm wavelength. Under clear conditions 1380 nm is fully absorbed by the earth's atmosphere and is observed at the top of the atmosphere only when reflected by cirrus clouds above 6 km. From this fact it is straightforward to analyze just the 1380 nm image plane and use the percentage of pixels that exceed a threshold as the cirrus cloud percentage and include it in the scene index database. This percentage allows a user to search for imagery with a low percentage of cloud cover. The pixels themselves are the basis of a cirrus cloud map. This capability greatly reduces the need to browse through large numbers of images to find one suitable for use.

The VNIR cloud estimate will make use of two bands used in the production of the RGB browse image. Provided that RGB browse image uses as band assignment B=450 nm, R=660 nm, and G=860 nm, the Normalized Vegetation Difference Index (NVDI) can be computed as $NVDI = (860 \text{ nm} - 660 \text{ nm}) / (860 \text{ nm} + 660 \text{ nm})$. Irrespective of whether vegetation is present, most of the earth's surface has spectra

rising in the near-IR. Since clouds do not share this spectral characteristic, values of NVDI below a threshold signal indicate that lower altitude clouds are likely blocking a ground image.

Beyond the cloud percentage estimates an even more powerful item will be stored in the scene index database. One of the products produced by the onboard ORASIS processing is the endmember file. Endmembers represent the unique spectral signatures contained in a scene as observed at the top of the atmosphere. The key aspect of the ORASIS endmember file is data volume. A raw 30 km by 200 km NEMO hypercube is 7500 Mbytes; ORASIS compressed data is approximately 375 Mbytes. However, the endmember file of this compressed data is only 0.3 Mbytes. Therefore, while the entire ORASIS file resides on a tape archive, the endmember data is small enough to store in a database. This allows the endmembers to be directly queried against the existence of spectral signature of interest.

Research is required to prove the concept, but it should be possible to match these endmembers to measured spectra of known objects. If this is the case, a "Spectral Spider" technique could be used to sift through all of the endmembers in the NEMO database to identify specific scenes that contain specific spectral signatures. This approach would provide a powerful data mining technique that could filter terabytes of imagery data to automatically locate a small subset appropriate to expensive, time-intensive, and detailed human analysis.

Data Delivery to the Naval User

Once the level 1B data is produced at the IPC a copy will be delivered to the Navy Operations Center (NOC) at NRL. This data transfer will be done via landline or physical delivery of a data tape. The NOC will be configured with a UNIX based workstation, a 100 GB RAID array, and a DLT based terabyte archive system. An uninterruptable power supply (UPS) will protect this system from abrupt shutdowns. The workstation will handle all input/output (I/O) on the archive. Also connected to the workstation will be a multi-processor PC running database, image processing, and web serving software. The NOC will also be equipped with Compact Disc/Digital Versatile Disc (CD/DVD) writers and a large format color printer in order to deliver imagery data to researchers and other customers. Finally, the NOC will be equipped with two workstations for NRL engineers to access NEMO telemetry from the DOC for use in anomaly resolution.

NRL researchers are currently developing multiple hyperspectral data processing algorithms that will measure bathymetry, bottom type, and water clarity and produce models for the Naval warfighter. These algorithms are being developed to provide an automated data processing path. This automation will allow remote users to request level 4 data products on-line. Applied Coherent Technology Corporation is providing the image processing tool, ProView Web, to exercise these algorithms in an automated fashion. ProView Web will allow NEMO data users to access and browse the entire database of collected NEMO

imagery. As with data requests, users will be able to search the database via text base entries or with an interactive map. Search results will display the RGB images for the scenes that match the search parameters. Once a desired scene is found the user has three options. First, the user may request delivery of the level 1B file of the scene. This delivery may be done electronically or by optical media. Second, the user may request additional processing on the level 1B file. This additional processing could produce any of the available products up to level 4. These results will be displayed on the web interface and made available to the user in the same manner as the level 1B file. Finally, a user may request delivery of level 4 data products as maps and charts. These options provide broad support to many users based on both the sophistication of analysis tools available and on the network bandwidth available.

Figure 3 shows an example of the ProView Web interface.

3. CONCLUSION

The NEMO program will image large volumes of hyperspectral and panchromatic imagery. In order to facilitate both user requests and data delivery to users, a web-based interface will be employed. Many of the steps in this data flow will be automated. Where applicable, the advantages derived from hyperspectral data will be achieved in the data flow. These advantages will permit more efficient searches for data, powerful data mining capabilities, and broad distribution of hyperspectral derived data products.

4. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Figure 3. ProView Web Interface

6. BIOGRAPHY

William Vincent is an Aerospace Engineer at the Naval Research Laboratory. He is currently serving as both the mission operations lead and launch vehicle integration lead on the NEMO program. He has been program manager on the Breakout Information Age Technology program and the Advanced Fiber Optic Sensing Program. He has worked at NRL since 1994. He received a BS in Aerospace Engineering from the University of Maryland in 1992. He performed research on space telerobotics to receive an MS from the University of Maryland in 1994.